
Osmotic Technology for Oral Drug Delivery: A Review of Current Status and Future Prospects

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Abstract Osmotically regulated oral drug delivery systems employ osmotic pressure as a mechanism to regulate the release of active pharmaceutical ingredients. The drug delivery mechanisms employed by these systems are largely unaffected by the physiological variables of the gastrointestinal tract. Consequently, these systems have the potential to be used for both systemic and targeted drug administration. The controlled release of pharmaceutical substances from osmotic systems is influenced by several formulation factors, including the solubility and osmotic pressure of the core components, the dimensions of the delivery orifice, and the characteristics of the rate-controlling membrane. Through the optimization of formulation and processing parameters, the development of osmotic systems becomes feasible for the controlled delivery of medications with varying characteristics. The typical drug delivery method exhibits a dosage pattern that leads to fluctuating and unpredictable plasma concentrations. This approach has limited control over the release of the medication and minimal impact on achieving effective concentrations at the desired spot. The challenges associated with traditional drug delivery can be overcome by deploying osmotic drug delivery systems, which represent a promising approach that leverages osmotic pressure to achieve regulated and optimal release of active medicinal components. The release of pharmaceuticals from these systems is influenced by several formulation parameters, such as the osmotic pressure exerted by the core components, the solubility of the drug, and the size of the delivery orifice in relation to the properties of the semipermeable membrane. Nevertheless, it operates independently from the anatomical surroundings of the gastrointestinal tract and the simultaneous consumption of meals. The objective of this book is to examine previous iterations of osmotic pumps, elucidating their operational principles as well as their constraints, while also exploring innovative methodologies that offer notable advantages compared to their predecessors. The present paper comprehensively addresses the various facets of the osmotic drug delivery system, encompassing its fundamental principle of osmosis, historical context, merits and demerits, fundamental constituents, diverse elements impacting its design, different classifications, and criteria for evaluation. This study presents novel methodologies for osmotic medication delivery systems and discusses their potential future applications.

Keywords Sitagliptin, DPP-4 inhibitor, Osmotic Technology, Oral Drug Delivery

Drug delivery System [1-3]

Drug delivery refers to the various methods, compositions, technologies, and systems employed to transport a substance within the body in order to achieve its intended therapeutic effect in a safe manner. The subject matter may encompass the precise localization of drugs within specific anatomical sites, or it may involve enhancing the

overall distribution and elimination of drugs throughout the body. Regardless, this field of study is primarily focused on assessing and optimizing the amount and duration of drug presence. Drug delivery is commonly addressed through the chemical composition of drugs; however, it can also encompass the utilization of medical equipment or the combination of drugs and devices.

The utilization of drug delivery technology alters the manner in which drugs are released, absorbed, distributed, and eliminated. This modification aims to enhance the effectiveness and safety of the product, while also enhancing patient convenience and adherence. The release of drugs occurs through several routes, including diffusion, degradation, swelling, and affinity-based processes.

Novel drug delivery system

Within the realm of drug delivery systems, innovative carriers have emerged that possess distinct advantages when compared to standard dosage forms. Conventional dosage forms are characterized by high dosages and limited bioavailability, instability, susceptibility to first-pass metabolism, volatility in plasma drug levels, and fast drug release.

The novel drug delivery system is a crucial instrument within the pharmaceutical industry, particularly in developed drug markets. The utilization of a novel medication delivery system has the potential to mitigate several challenges by improving the effectiveness, safety, adherence of patients, and longevity of the product [4].

Osmotic drug delivery System:

The field of osmotic drug delivery systems has witnessed significant advancements since the development of an implantable pump by Australian physiologists Rose and Nelson in 1955. The osmotic drug delivery system is employed to provide regulated drug release by utilizing osmogens and harnessing osmotic pressure, with a duration of up to 10-16 hours. Osmotic systems have been widely adopted for regulated drug-delivery applications, demonstrating their efficacy in both human medicines and veterinary medicine [5].

Oral drug delivery methods are recognized for their ability to rapidly release drugs, but they lack control over drug release and fail to sustain optimal concentrations at the intended site for extended durations. A limited number of studies have previously examined one-compartment and two-compartment osmotic systems [7-10].

The osmotically regulated drug delivery system has a high degree of drug release, and its delivery mechanism is not influenced by the physiological variables of the gastrointestinal tract. These systems have the potential to be employed for both systemic and targeted drug delivery purposes. Osmotically regulated oral medication delivery systems employ osmotic pressure as a means of regulating the release of active drugs [11].

The Osmotic Pump Controlled Release Preparation is an innovative drug delivery system that exhibits a constant drug release rate, which is regulated by the osmotic pressure gradient between the interior and exterior of the semi-permeable membrane serving as the driving force for drug delivery [12].

Osmosis is characterized as the autonomous movement of a solvent across an ideal semi-permeable membrane, from a solution with a lower concentration of solute to a solution with a higher concentration of solute. This process occurs exclusively through the membrane's permeability to the solvent, while remaining impermeable to the solute. The phenomenon whereby the application of pressure on the side with increased solute concentration hinders the movement of solvent molecules is referred to as osmotic pressure [13].

The controlled release of drugs in these systems is facilitated by utilizing osmotic pressure as the driving mechanism [14]. Traditional drug delivery systems exhibit little control over the release of drugs and lack the ability to regulate the concentration of drugs at the desired location. The osmotic pump tablet typically comprises a central component containing the medication, an osmotic agent, other excipients, and a semipermeable membrane coating. This study primarily focuses on the fundamental components of osmotic systems [15].

The controlled release system is designed to ensure the sustained administration of a medicine over an extended duration, without interruption, as predetermined. The system regulates the levels of drugs in the specific tissues or cells. Controlled release is a dominant presence in the market due to its several advantages over conventional dose forms, such as simplified administration, decreased dosing frequency, and improved patient adherence. The primary

objective of controlled drug delivery systems is to enhance the efficacy of medication therapies through the extended and sustained release of the drug over a protracted duration [16].

Conventional oral drug delivery methods are recognized for their ability to achieve prompt drug release, but they lack the capacity to regulate the release of the medication and sustain optimal concentration levels at the intended site for extended durations. The variability in the bioavailability of a drug across different formulations can be attributed to several factors, including the physico-chemical properties of the drug, the presence of excipients, and various physiological factors such as the presence or absence of food, the pH of the gastrointestinal tract, and gastrointestinal motility. The limitation of the oral route is addressed by the parenteral route. This particular pathway presents the benefit of decreased dosage, precise targeting of the intended region, and the avoidance of gastrointestinal instability and hepatic bypass of the drug molecule. In recent years, there has been significant progress in pharmaceutical research, resulting in the emergence of multiple innovative drug delivery systems. Osmotic systems employ the principles of osmotic pressure to facilitate drug delivery through both oral and parenteral routes [17].

Osmosis

The initial documentation of an osmotic phenomenon can be traced back to Abbenollet's publication in 1748. However, it was in 1877 that Pfeffer achieved the initial quantitative measurement. The experiment involves the utilization of a selectively permeable membrane that allows for the passage of water molecules while preventing the passage of sugar molecules. This membrane is employed to separate a solution containing sugar from pure water. A continuous influx of water occurs within the sugar solution, which persists until a pressure π is exerted onto the sugar solution. Pfeffer's research demonstrated a direct relationship between the osmotic pressure (π) of a sugar solution and both the concentration of the solution and the temperature. In a short span of time, Vant Hoff demonstrated the correlation between these findings and the principles of ideal gas laws by the given expression.

$$\pi = \Phi c r t$$

Where;

Φ = osmotic coefficient of the solution,

c = molar concentration of sugar in the solution,

r = gas constant,

t = absolute temperature.

The osmotic pressure of concentrated solutions containing soluble solutes, which are frequently employed in controlled release formulations, is notably elevated. This range spans from 30 atm for sodium phosphate to 500 atm for a mixture of lactose and fructose. The high osmotic pressure of these solutes facilitates a substantial flow of water across a semi-permeable membrane. The equation provided represents the osmotic water flow across a membrane.

$$Dv/dt = A Q \Delta \pi / L$$

dv/dt = water flow across the membrane of area

A = thickness L, and the permeability

Q in cm^2

$\Delta \pi$ is the osmotic pressure difference between the two solutions on either side of the membrane.

This equation pertains exclusively to a fully permeable membrane that selectively allows the passage of water while totally preventing the passage of the osmotic agent [18].

Osmosis is a phenomenon characterized by the spontaneous movement of a solvent across an ideal semipermeable membrane, from a solution with a lower concentration of solute to a solution with a higher concentration of solute. This movement is driven by a disparity in osmotic pressure across the membrane, which is permeable solely to the solvent and impermeable to solute molecules or ions. The phenomenon of applying pressure to the side with a higher concentration in order to impede the movement of solvent is referred to as osmotic pressure. Osmotic pressure refers to the pressure that, when exerted on the solution with a higher concentration, would hinder the movement of water across the semipermeable membrane.

Mechanism of osmosis

The core of the formulation consists of a water-soluble osmotically active agent, which is combined with a water-soluble or insoluble medication, additives, and a coating that acts as a semi-permeable membrane. The barrier only allows for the permeation of water, leading to the dissolution of the essential component of the core upon initial water penetration. Consequently, an osmotic pressure disparity is established across the membrane. The device is capable of delivering a volume that is saturated, which is equivalent to the volume of water that is absorbed through the membrane. The initial lag time, expressed per hour, corresponds to the period in which the delivery rate gradually increases to reach its maximum value. During this time, drug release follows a zero-order kinetics until all solid material is dissolved. The Van't Hoff equation describes the relationship between osmotic pressure (π) and the concentration of a non-electrolyte in a dilute solution that can be assumed to exhibit perfect behavior.

$$\pi V = nRT$$

Where, V = is the volume of solution.

n = is number of moles of solute.

T = thermodynamic temperature and

R = is the gas constant

Osmotic pressure is a colligative phenomenon shown by solutions, wherein the osmotic pressure magnitude remains unaffected by the quantity of individual solute entities present in the solution. The regulation of medication distribution from an osmotic device is facilitated by the osmotic pressure generated as a result of the imbibition of fluid from the external environment into the dosage form. The rate of drug distribution from an osmotic pump is directly proportional to the osmotic pressure generated as a result of fluid imbibition by osmosis [19].

e.g. ∴ Potassium chloride 245,

Sodium chloride 356, etc.

The osmotic pressure can also be found out by the Van't Hoff equation [20-21]

$$\pi = CRT$$

Where,

π = Osmotic pressure of the solution,

C = Molar concentration of the solute in the solution,

R = Gas constant,

T = Absolute temperature.

Osmotically regulated oral drug delivery systems employ osmotic pressure as the primary mechanism for the controlled release of pharmaceutical substances. [22]. The most straightforward and reliable method to maintain a consistent osmotic pressure is by ensuring that the compartment contains a saturated solution of the osmotic agent. The subsequent table presents data on the osmotic pressure of frequently employed solutes in controlled-release formulations [23].

Principle

An osmotic system is designed to provide a therapeutic drug at a constant rate, following a zero-order release pattern. This mechanism operates on the principle of osmosis, whereby a solvent moves from an area of lower solute concentration to an area of greater solute concentration through a semi-permeable membrane. Following the administration of an osmotic system, water is absorbed into the core osmotically via a semi-permeable membrane, leading to the generation of hydrostatic pressure. This pressure facilitates the expulsion of a drug-containing solution or suspension from the core through one or more delivery ports. The regulation of the system's supply is governed by the ingress of water via a semipermeable membrane [19].

Advantages

- The predictability of the release rate in osmotic systems is notably high and can be effectively regulated by the modulation of release control parameters.
- The attainment of a zero-order delivery rate can be accomplished by the utilization of osmotic systems.
- The frequency of dosage with osmotic pump tablets is decreased as a result of the medicine being delivered over an extended duration, in contrast to traditional tablets.
- The attainment of a zero-order delivery rate can be accomplished by the utilization of osmotic systems.
- The delivery of goods or services may experience delays or be conducted in a pulsed manner, if so desired.
- Osmotic systems have the potential to achieve higher release rates in comparison to conventional drug delivery systems that are diffusion-controlled.
- In the case of oral osmotic systems, the release of drugs is not influenced by variations in gastric pH or hydrodynamic circumstances.
- The presence of food in the gastrointestinal track has limited impact on the release of substances from osmotic systems.
- A significant level of correlation between in vivo and in vitro behavior, known as in vivo-in vitro correlation (IVIVC), is achieved in osmotic systems.

Disadvantages

- Specialized equipment is necessary for creating an opening within the system.
- High cost.
- The occurrence of toxicity resulting from the phenomenon of dosage dumping.
- The phenomenon of tolerance developing quickly.

Basic Components of Osmotic Systems**Drug**

Ideal characteristics for osmotic systems include substances with short biological half-lives and those that are suitable for sustained treatment. Several medication candidates, including Diltiazem HCl, Carbamazepine, Metoprolol, Oxprenolol, and others, are formulated using osmotic administration systems.

Semi-permeable membrane

The semi-permeable membrane housing plays a crucial role in the osmotic medication delivery system. Hence, the careful choice of a polymeric membrane is crucial for the development of an osmotic delivery system. The membrane must exhibit specific attributes, including impermeability to the transit of pharmaceuticals and other constituents found within the compartments. The membrane must possess inert characteristics and retain its dimensional integrity in order to ensure a consistent osmotic driving force throughout the process of drug delivery [24]. Polymeric materials with the characteristic of allowing water permeation while effectively preventing solute permeation can serve as suitable coating materials for osmotic devices. For instance, examples of cellulose esters include cellulose acetate, cellulose acetate butyrate, cellulose triacetate, and ethyl cellulose, as well as Eudragits [25].

Flux regulators

Delivery systems have the capability to control the fluid's permeability through the inclusion of flux-regulating agents within the layer. The inclusion of hydrophilic substances, such as polyethylene glycols with molecular weights ranging from 300 to 6000 Daltons, polyhydric alcohols, and polyalkylene glycols, has been observed to enhance the flux. Conversely, the presence of hydrophobic materials, such as phthalates that have been substituted with alkyl or alkoxy groups (e.g., diethyl phthalate or dimethoxy ethylphthalate), has been found to have a diminishing effect on the flux. Materials that are considerably impermeable to water, such as insoluble salts or insoluble oxides, can likewise be utilized for this particular objective [26].

Coating solvent

In the production of the osmotic device's wall, appropriate solvents are employed to create a polymeric solution. These solvents, both inorganic and organic, are selected based on their inert nature and their ability to avoid causing any detrimental effects to the core, wall, and other constituent materials. Common solvents commonly used in many applications include methylene chloride, acetone, methanol, ethanol, isopropyl alcohol, butyl alcohol, ethyl acetate, cyclohexane, carbon tetrachloride, and water, among others. Various solvent mixes, including acetone-methanol (80:20), acetone-ethanol (80:20), acetone-water (90:10), methylene chloride-methanol (79:21), and methylene chloride-methanol-water (75:22:3), among others, can be employed [27].

Wicking agent

A wicking agent can be classified as either swellable or non-swellable in its nature. These entities possess the capacity to conduct physiosorption in the presence of water. Physiosorption refers to a type of absorption process wherein solvent molecules can weakly attach to the surface of the wicking agent through Van der Waals interactions between the wicking agent's surface and the absorbed molecule. The primary role of the wicking agent is to facilitate the transportation of water towards the internal regions of the tablet core, resulting in the formation of channels or an interconnected network that enhances the overall surface area. Suitable materials that can function as wicking agents encompass colloidal silicon dioxide, kaolin, titanium dioxide, alumina, niacinamide, sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), low molecular weight poly (vinyl pyrrolidone) PVP, m-pyrol, bentonite, magnesium aluminium silicate, polyester, and polyethylene. SLS, colloidal silica, and PVP are examples of non-swellable wicking agents [28].

Pore forming agent

The pore-forming chemicals induce the creation of a membrane with micro porous structure. The formation of the micro-porous wall can occur in situ through the leaching of a pore-former during system operation. Pore-formers can exist in either inorganic or organic forms, and can be found in either solid or liquid states. For instance, pore forming agents can include alkaline metal salts, such as sodium chloride, sodium bromide, potassium chloride, potassium sulphate, and potassium phosphate, as well as alkaline earth metals, such as calcium chloride and calcium nitrate. Additionally, carbohydrates like sucrose, glucose, fructose, mannose, lactose, sorbitol, and mannitol, along with diols and polyols such as polyhydric alcohols, polyethylene glycols, and polyvinyl pyrrolidone, can also serve as pore forming agents [29].

Plasticizers [30]

The formulation of osmotic systems is significantly influenced by the types and quantities of plasticizers employed in coating membranes. Polymers have the potential to undergo alterations in their visco-elastic properties, which in turn can have an impact on the permeability characteristics of polymeric films. The plasticizers employed include the following.

Polyethylene glycols Ethylene glycol monoacetate

Diacetate- for low permeability Tri ethyl citrate

Diethyl tartarate or Diacetin- for more permeable films

Osmotic agent [31-33]

These substances are alternatively referred to as osmogents and serve the purpose of generating osmotic pressure within the system. When the solubility of a drug is poor, the drug will exhibit zero-order release, albeit at a reduced pace. In order to augment the pace at which the release occurs, an osmotic agent is incorporated into the formulation. The utilization of an osmotic agent induces a significant osmotic pressure gradient within the system, hence augmenting the rate at which the medicine is released.

Some of the commercially used Osmotic Agents:

- Sodium chloride
- Fructose

- Sucrose
- Potassium chloride
- Xylitol
- Sorbitol
- Citric acid
- Dextrose,
- Mannitole
- Lactose.

Some Mixture used as an Osmotic Agents:

- Dextrose +Fructose
- Lactose +Fructose
- Sucrose+ Fructose
- Lactose +Dextrose
- Mannitol +Fructose
- Mannitol +Dextrose
- Dextrose +Sucrose
- Mannitol +Sucrose

Classification

The classification of osmotic drug delivery system. They fall in two categories.

- A. Implantable Osmotic Pump
- B. Oral osmotic Pump

A. Implantable Osmotic Pump**1) The Rose-Nelson Pump**

In the year 1955, Rose and Nelson were the first to apply the principle of osmosis to the field of drug delivery [37]. The authors provided a description of two systems capable of administering medication at precise dosages, specifically 0.02 ml per day over a period of 100 days and 0.5 ml per day for a duration of four days. Figure 3A presents a schematic diagram depicting the Rose-Nelson pump. The device consists of three distinct chambers: the first chamber serves as a medication reservoir, the second chamber contains salt, and the third chamber contains water. The separation between the salt chamber and the water chamber is achieved through the use of a semipermeable solid membrane, whilst the drug chamber is isolated from the salt chamber by an elastic diaphragm. Over a period of time, the process of osmotic imbibition, wherein water permeates through the semipermeable membrane (SPM), leads to an augmentation in the volume of the salt chamber. This rise in volume causes a disturbance in the elastic diaphragm, ultimately resulting in the expulsion of the drug from the delivery system via the delivery orifice. The discharge of the medication from the system is facilitated by the osmotic pressure exerted by the saturated salt solution in the chamber. Hence, provided that a enough quantity of solid salt is present within the salt chamber, the rate at which water permeates through the solid phase matrix (SPM) remains consistent, resulting in a constant rate of drug release.

One of the problems with the Rose-Nelson pump is that the osmotic flow occurs as soon as the salt chamber meets the water. Therefore, the pump had to be kept empty and to be loaded with water immediately before use, which make a process that was problematic for delivery of drugs. Moreover, although these systems have a large amount of research, their complex design makes them poor system in large-scale production which makes them of limited use.

The Rose-Nelson pump rate is provided by Equation.

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = \frac{dV}{dt} * C$$

Where

$\frac{dM}{dt}$ = drug release rate

$\frac{dV}{dt}$ = the volume flow of water into the salt chamber

c = the concentration of drug in the drug chamber.

2) **Alzet osmotic pump [38,39]**

The functionality of ALZET pumps is attributed to the osmotic pressure disparity between the inner chamber of the pump, referred to as the salt sleeves, and the specific tissue region where the pump is surgically placed. The flow of water into the tap is facilitated by the semipermeable membrane (SPM) as a result of the elevated osmolality of the salt sleeve, which is situated on the outer surface of the pump. The ingress of water into the salt sleeve results in the compression of the pliable reservoir, so facilitating the regulated extraction of the test solution from the pump at a predetermined rate. One limitation of pumps is their single-use design, as the compressed reservoir cannot be replenished, so restricting their reusability.

3) **Higuchi – Leeper Pump [40-42, 61]**

During the 1970s, Higuchi and Leeper made several alterations to the pump originally developed by Rose Nelson. One significant alteration to their proposed design involves the elimination of the water chamber within the device and the utilization of the surrounding environment to obtain water through the process of self-propelled motion (SPM). Figure 3A depicts the formal representation of the pump. The significance of this invention stems from its reliance on immersion in a liquid environment for functionality, as well as its ability to be preserved for extended periods of time prior to utilization. Nevertheless, the intricate configuration and multitude of pump elements continue to hinder its widespread use in industrial-scale manufacturing.

4) **Higuchi – Theeuwes Pump[41,43,61]**

During the early 1970s, Higuchi and Theeuwes devised an alternative approach that had resemblance to the simplification of the Rose-Nelson pump. As depicted in Figure 3A, the pump comprises a suspended particulate matter (SPM) enveloping a solid salt layer. The flexible diaphragm envelops the inner surface of the salt layer, establishing contact with the inside of the device housing an active pharmaceutical component. Similar to the Higuchi-Leeper tap, the acquisition of water necessary for the osmotic function of the pump is contingent upon the presence of an adjacent aqueous environment. In contrast, the Higuchi-Theeuwes method eliminates the stiff housing and instead utilizes a membrane as the external enclosure of the pump. The membrane has a high level of strength, enabling it to effectively endure the internal pressure generated by the pump within the system. The medicine of interest is placed into the device prior to its utilization. The drug release in a liquid environment is determined by the temporal pattern established by the salt employed in the salt chamber and the permeability of the outside membrane casing. The majority of Higuchi- Theeuwes pumps employ a solid salt disperser within a salt chamber that is appropriate for the system.

B. Oral Osmotic Pump

1) Single Chamber Osmotic Pump

i. Elementary Osmotic Pump

Significant advancements in the field of osmotic pumps occurred in 1975, when Theeuwes made further improvements to the Rose-Nelson pump, resulting in the invention of a more streamlined device referred to as the elementary osmotic pump. The user's text does not provide any information to rewrite in an academic manner. The fundamental structure of the osmotic pump comprises an osmotic core enveloped by a semipermeable membrane (SPM) that includes the orifice responsible for drug release.

When immersed in a liquid medium, the dissimilarity in osmotic pressure induces the movement of water towards the tablet across a semi-permeable membrane (SPM), resulting in the formation of a homogeneous solution within the enclosed osmotic pump (EOP). The continual consumption of water results in an increase in tablet volume,

hence causing the tablet to experience hydrostatic pressure. The hydrostatic pressure is released from the solution of a complete drug solution through the delivery orifice, as the system is enveloped by a solid phase microextraction (SPM). The dissolution of the soluble core proceeds steadily until it is fully dissolved. Upon complete dissolution, the process of drug administration persists at diminishing rates until the osmotic pressure disparity across the membrane approaches null.

The subsequent significant determinant in regulating osmotic medication release pertains to the disparity in osmotic pressure across the membrane. In the context of zero-order drug release, it is imperative that the osmotic pressure differential rapidly reaches a steady state and maintains a consistent value during the intended duration of drug release. The maintenance of a saturated solution of the medication in the core is the method employed in osmotic pumps to achieve this. If the drug solution is unable to generate adequate osmotic pressure, it is necessary to incorporate supplementary osmotic agents into the core formulation.

The characteristics of the membrane have a significant role in governing the release of drugs. The membrane ought to exhibit selective permeability exclusively to water, so enabling regulated ingress of water into the tablet. Cellulose esters, such as cellulose acetate, cellulose diacetate, cellulose triacetate, cellulose propionate, cellulose acetate butyrate, and various others, are among the polymers commonly employed as coatings in osmotic delivery systems [43]. Other polymers used are ethylcellulose [44] and Eudragits [45].

The dimension of the medication delivery orifice is a crucial factor in regulating the rate of release. In the case of simple osmotic pumps, it is imperative that the dimensions of the delivery orifice adhere to two specific criteria. There are two primary considerations for the size of the orifice in the tablet delivery system. Firstly, the orifice should be of a size that effectively reduces the hydrostatic pressure within the tablet, as this pressure might impact the zero-order discharge rate. Secondly, the aperture should be small enough to minimize its impact on the overall drug release process, allowing for easy diffusion of the drug through the orifice. Equations exist for the estimation of the minimum and maximum width of the orifice area [36].

Table 1: Osmotic Pressure of Saturated Solutions of Common Pharmaceutical Solutes

Compound or Mixture	Osmotic Pressure (atm.)
Lactose-fructose	500
Dextrose-fructose	450
Sucrose-fructose	430
Mannitol-fructose	415
Sodium chloride	356
Fructose	335
Lactose-sucrose	250
Potassium chloride	245
Lactose-dextrose	225
Mannitol-dextrose	225
Dextrose-sucrose	190
Mannitol-sucrose	170
Sucrose	150
Mannitol-lactose	130
Dextrose	82
Potassium sulfate	39
Mannitol	38
Sodium phosphate tribasic. 12 H ₂ O	36
Sodium phosphate dibasic .7 H ₂ O	31
Sodium phosphate dibasic. 12 H ₂ O	31
Sodium phosphate dibasic anhydrous	29

2) Multi Chamber Osmotic Pump

i. Push Pull Osmotic Pump

The aforementioned apparatus is a customized version of an elementary osmotic pump, designed as an osmotically multi-chamber tablet. The osmotic pumps consist of two chambers and are categorized into two primary parts based on whether one chamber exhibits expansion into the other or if the chambers remain rigid and do not undergo expansion.

Tablets containing expansion (push) layer are the most important one [47,48]. This device is designed for the delivery of drug with poor water solubility and is indicated by a scheme in figure 1 [49]. The structure comprises of a dual-layer configuration, encompassed by a solid impermeable membrane. The upper stratum, sometimes referred to as the pull layer, encompasses the drug substance and is interconnected with the external environment through the delivery orifice. The lower layer, characterized by the presence of a polymeric agent, lacks a designated region for the release of substances. When the dosage form is exposed to a liquid environment, the process of osmosis causes water to be drawn into both components. Due to the absence of a delivery region in the bottom chamber, it undergoes expansion and exerts pressure on the pull layer, causing it to move towards the top side (in the direction of the delivery orifice). As a result, the medication in solution form is transmitted through the delivery aperture.

The medication solution was diluted by a two-step process.

- a) The process of osmotic water imbibition facilitates the solubilization of a medication within the pull chamber. Nevertheless, the medication is unable to exit the apparatus until it traverses a secondary compartment.
- b) The movement of water by osmosis into the second chamber results in the dilution of the drug solution prior to its exit from the delivery system.

Figure 1: Mechanism of Drug Delivery from a Push-Pull

ii. Osmotic Pump with Non-Expanding Second Chamber

These devices are equipped with systems that incorporate a second chamber that is non-expandable. The primary objective of the second chamber is to attenuate the drug solution emanating from the device, so facilitating the treatment of medications that induce significant gastrointestinal irritation. Additionally, it enables the concurrent administration of two distinct pharmaceuticals. This type of device can be utilized for the delivery of poorly soluble or insoluble medicines through their formulation [35].

3) Modified Osmotic Pump

i. Controlled Porosity Osmotic Pump (CPOP)

The controlled osmotic porosity pump is equipped with a coated membrane that incorporates water-soluble additives. Upon exposure to a liquid environment, these additives dissolve, leading to the creation of a microporous membrane in situ, as depicted in Figure 2.

The controlled porosity wall can be characterized by its sponge-like morphology. In general, materials that exhibit a range of porosity between 5% and 95%, with pore sizes spanning from 10 angstroms to 100 micrometers, can be employed [46,47,49,50]. The resultant membrane exhibits permeability to both dissolved solutes and water. Various water-soluble additives employed for this objective encompass dimethyl sulfone, saccharides, amino acids, sorbitol, among others [51]. In a study conducted by Ying-Ku Lin (2003), the focus was on investigating the mechanism

behind the release of pharmaceuticals with moderate-to-high solubility. This was achieved by utilizing several solubility modifying agents [52].

Figure 2: *Controlled Porosity Osmotic Pump (CPOP)*

ii. Osmotically Rupturable Pumps

Another widely recognized classification pertains to osmotic systems, which facilitate the controlled release of the active substance via an osmotic bursting mechanism. The device was devised by Baker and comprises an osmotic core enveloped by a self-propelled micromotor (SPM) [53]. When immersed in a liquid medium, water is osmotically attracted into the device, resulting in membrane swelling. The aforementioned procedure persists until the internal pressure within the apparatus surpasses the cohesive strength of the membrane, leading to the rupture of the membrane in a region of reduced strength, typically near its periphery. When the membrane is ruptured, the device exhibits characteristics similar to an elementary osmotic pump, whereby the medicinal molecule is extracted from the cracked region by the process of osmotic pumping.

Rapture time of SPM can be controlled by.

- a) Varying type, area or thickness of SPM
- b) Altering the osmotic agents embedded in the osmotic core.

iii. Liquid Oral Osmotic System (L-OROS)

There are several LOROS systems that are utilized for the purpose of controlled administration of liquid formulations. These systems include the L-OROS soft cap, L-OROS hard cap, and a delayed liquid bolus delivery system. Each of these systems comprises a liquid drug layer, an osmotic engine or Push layer, and an SPM (Figure 3).

Upon contact with water, the system undergoes water penetration through the surface plasmon resonance (SPM) mechanism, subsequently triggering the activation of an osmotic layer. The enlargement of the osmotic layer results in the generation of hydrostatic pressure within the system, consequently compelling the liquid formulation to be expelled from the orifice at the delivery point [34]. While, L-OROS hard caps and L-OROS soft cap systems are designed to provide continuous drug delivery, the L-OROS delayed delivery of liquid bolus system is designed to deliver pulse of liquid drug [54].

Figure 3: Cross-sectional Diagram of Liquid Oral Osmotic System (L-OROS)

iv. Colon Targeted Oral Osmotic System (OROS-CT)

The OROS-CT system is employed for the targeted administration of drugs to the colon region, allowing for once or twice day dosing. The composition consists of a hard gelatin capsule containing 5-6 enteric-coated push-pull osmotic units, designed to facilitate precise medication administration to the colon region. The user's text is too short to be rewritten in an academic manner. Upon exposure to gastrointestinal (GI) fluid, the gelatin capsule undergoes dissolution, while the enteric coating acts as a barrier, preventing the influx of stomach fluid into the system (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Cross-sectional Diagram of OROS-CT Delivery System

Upon entering the small intestine, the OROS-CT system undergoes dissolution of its enteric coating. This dissolution leads to the influx of water into the core of the system, resulting in the expansion of the push layer. During this period, a gel with fluid-like properties is generated within the drug layer, subsequently being discharged through the orifice at a meticulously regulated pace determined by the water transport rate over the semi-permeable membrane (SPM). Approximately 80% of the medicine is delivered to the large intestine by the use of OROS-CT.

v. Sandwiched Osmotic Tablets (SOTS)

The structure comprises of a central polymeric layer, flanked by two drug layers, each including two delivery orifices [34]. Upon immersion in a liquid medium, (Figure 5) [55] the center push layer, which comprises a swellable polymer, undergoes swelling, leading to the release of the medication from the delivery hole. One advantage of this particular system lies in its mechanism of drug extrusion from two opposing layers within the tablet. Consequently, this technique, known as SOTS, may be considered appropriate for medications that have a propensity to induce irritation of the stomach mucosa, namely within the abdominal cord.

Figure 5: Schematic Diagram of Sandwiched Osmotic Tablet (SOTS)

vi. Osmotic Pump for Insoluble Drugs

The process involves the application of a surface protective material (SPM) onto the particles of the osmotic agent, also known as osmogens. The particles are combined with an insoluble drug component and compacted into a tablet shape. Subsequently, they are enclosed within a semipermeable membrane (SPM), and a small opening is created in the membrane [32].

Upon coming into contact with the liquid, the water is transported across both layers towards the particles of the osmotic agent. Subsequently, the water expands and exerts hydrostatic pressure to propel the medicine through a delivery aperture [56].

vii. Monolithic Osmotic Systems

The composition consists of a straightforward dispersion of a chemical that is soluble in water inside a polymeric matrix. Upon exposure to a liquid medium, the drug substance undergoes water absorption, leading to the rupture of the polymer matrix and subsequent release of the drug into the surrounding environment. The process commences on the external surface of the polymer matrix and subsequently advances towards the internal surface of the matrix in a uniform and sequential manner. Nevertheless, the efficacy of this system is compromised when the active drug introduced into the osmotic system exceeds 20 to 30% [57].

viii. Telescopic Capsule for Delayed Release

The apparatus is comprised of two compartments, with the initial compartment housing the delivery orifice and medicament, while the subsequent compartment houses the osmotic engine [58]. A layer with wax-like properties serves as a barrier between the two chambers. In order to construct the delivery apparatus, the pharmaceutical compound is introduced into one of the chambers utilizing either a human or automated filling mechanism. A bi-layered tablet containing an osmotic engine is positioned on the convex osmotic layer located at the distal end of the

capsule cap. The cap is closed, with a barrier layer covering the end, while the opening of the cap exposes a barrier layer. The open end of the filled vessel is affixed to the inner side of the cap's open end, and then the two components are compressed until the osmotic bilayer tablet, cap, and vessel are snugly fitted together. When fluid is introduced into the housing of the dispensing device, it will cause the osmotic engine to expand, thereby applying pressure on the interconnected parts of the second and first wall. The little flow of surrounding fluid generated by the pressure entering the reservoir results in the absence of agent delivery during that interval.

ix. Multiparticulate Delayed-Release System

The present approach involves the encapsulation of pellets containing a water-soluble medication, which may be combined with osmotic agents, followed by the application of a semi-permeable membrane (SPM) coating. Upon contact with water, the core absorbs water and creates a saturated solution of pharmacological compounds. The phenomenon of fluid influx is primarily driven by the osmotic pressure gradient, resulting in the rapid growth of fluid volume and subsequent expansion of the membrane, ultimately leading to the creation of pores. The liberation of pharmaceutical components via these apertures often adheres to zero-order kinetics. The findings of Schultz and Kleinebudde [59] indicate that the lag periods and release rates are influenced by the thickness of the coating layer and the osmotic pressure of the dissolution fluid.

x. Osmotic Matrix Tablet (OSMAT)

The system under consideration is an osmotically driven matrix system that employs a hydrophilic polymer material capable of swelling and gelling into a liquid state, resulting in a semi-permeable structure at the site of application. The liberation from a matrix system that encompasses osmogen can be influenced by the phenomenon of osmosion. The OSMAT approach incorporates both matrix and osmotic principles, resulting in significant advancements in drug delivery from swellable matrix devices. Osmotic matrix tablets are characterized by their ease of production and their ability to release drugs without the need for SPM coating or aperture. Hence, it is a cost-effective approach that may be employed for a diverse range of pharmaceutical compounds [60, 62].

Conclusion

Osmotic pumps are a highly regulated approach to drug administration. Osmotic drug delivery systems typically consist of a drug component that incorporates an osmogen within its core, which is then enveloped by a semipermeable membrane. The coating possesses one or more apertures through which the medication solution or suspension is gradually discharged over a specified duration. In the context of osmotic delivery systems, the release of pharmaceuticals from the dosage form is hindered by the depletion of osmotic pressure at the delivery hole. The release of the medicine from the dosage form is facilitated by elevating the internal pressure resulting from water penetration. One of the primary advantages is the ability to maintain accurate control over the zero-order release for an extended duration. This means that a precise release rate may be achieved consistently, irrespective of the many environmental conditions present at the delivery location. The use of osmotic systems enables the achievement of a precise and controlled rate of drug release, which in turn helps to mitigate the occurrence of adverse effects by regulating the blood plasma concentrations of normal-dose forms, such as traditional instant release formulations. Consequently, a majority of the items currently available in the market are derived from pharmaceuticals utilized in the treatment of chronic conditions such as diabetes, hypertension, attention deficit disorder, and other enduring ailments. In addition to osmotic delivery systems, there is promise in utilizing osmotic systems for the distribution of diverse compounds at a specific rate over a prolonged duration. In the realm of future developments, many endeavors are underway to create an efficacious osmotic system, including but not limited to pulsatile delivery mechanisms with expandable orifices, lipid-based osmotic pumps, telescopic capsules housing compact osmotic pumps for delayed release, and osmotic bursting pumps.

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